

Aetiology and Clinical Pattern of Jaundice in a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Study of 100 Cases

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18 May 2026
Accepted: 23 May 2026
Published Online: 26 May 2026

DOI:

Volume: 9, Number: 3, Page: 241-247

e-ISSN: 2789-5912
ISSN: 2617-0817

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Jaundice is a common clinical manifestation of hepatobiliary and hematological disorders, frequently encountered in tertiary care hospitals in Bangladesh. The etiological spectrum varies widely, with viral hepatitis, obstructive biliary diseases, and hemolytic disorders being major contributors. Understanding the clinical, etiological, and investigative profile of jaundiced patients is essential for early diagnosis and appropriate management. **Aim of the Study:** To evaluate the aetiology and clinical pattern of jaundice in a tertiary care hospital. **Methods & Materials:** This cross-sectional observational hospital-based study was conducted in the medicine wards of Chittagong Medical College Hospital (CMCH), Chittagong, Bangladesh, over a period of 12 months. A total of 100 patients aged >12 years admitted with jaundice were included following informed consent. Patients ≤12 years, those managed exclusively on an outpatient basis, and those unwilling to participate were excluded. Data were collected using a structured case record form including demographic characteristics, clinical features, laboratory investigations, and imaging findings. Etiological classification into hepatocellular, obstructive, and haemolytic jaundice was established based on clinical, biochemical, and imaging criteria. Statistical analysis was performed using descriptive methods. **Results:** Out of 100 patients, hepatocellular jaundice was the most common (80%), followed by obstructive (16%) and haemolytic (4%). Viral hepatitis accounted for 43% of total cases, with hepatitis B virus (24%) and hepatitis E virus (18%) being predominant. Hepatocellular carcinoma constituted 15%, and chronic liver disease 10%. Among obstructive

causes, carcinoma of the common bile duct (4%), cholelithiasis (3%), and biliary ascariasis (3%) were most frequent. The peak age incidence was 31–40 years (28%), with a male predominance (63%, M:F = 1.7:1). Common symptoms included anorexia (87%), nausea/vomiting (80%), abdominal pain (79%), and fatigue (74%). Pruritus was markedly higher in obstructive jaundice (87.5%). Clinical examination revealed hepatomegaly in 67% and ascites in 28% (only in hepatocellular cases). Severe jaundice was observed in 36% of hepatocellular and 43.8% of obstructive cases. Laboratory findings showed markedly reduced hemoglobin in haemolytic jaundice (5.7 ± 1.2 g/dl), elevated ESR in obstructive (81.5 ± 46.2 mm/hr), and raised transaminases in hepatocellular cases (ALT >1000 IU/L in 12.5%). Serum bilirubin exceeded 30 mg/dl in 3.8% of hepatocellular and 12.5% of obstructive cases. Ultrasonography detected hepatomegaly in 50.8% of hepatocellular cases and identified all obstructive causes, including biliary masses and stones. **Conclusion:** Hepatocellular jaundice, predominantly due to viral hepatitis (HBV and HEV), is the leading cause of jaundice in hospitalized patients in Bangladesh. Clinical features combined with laboratory and ultrasonographic findings provide reliable differentiation among jaundice types. Early diagnosis and improved access to diagnostic facilities are crucial to reduce disease burden and complications.

Keywords: Jaundice, Hepatocellular, Obstructive, Haemolytic, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis E, Bangladesh, CMCH.

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INTRODUCTION

Jaundice or icterus is a condition recognized clinically by a yellowish discoloration of the skin and mucous membranes caused by the staining of tissues with bile pigment.^[1] The condition is quite prevalent in Bangladesh and can occur at all ages due to varying causes. In some cases, timely diagnosis can cure the condition and some are preventable, whereas others may be incurable. It is a common and almost unique clinical presentation of hepatobiliary problems encountered in day-to-day clinical practice.^[2] Among the causes of jaundice, hepatitis virus infection and hepatobiliary obstruction occupy the major percentage. Between 350 million to 400 million people worldwide are chronically infected with hepatitis B virus (HBV), and 15–20% of patients with chronic hepatitis B develop cirrhosis within 5 years, while over 250,000 patients worldwide die annually

from HBV-related liver diseases.^[3] In Bangladesh, the prevalence of HBV is 2.3% to 9.7% with an approximate carrier pool of 10 million.^[4] A substantial proportion of hospital-admitted chronic liver disease patients are likely to be chronic carriers of HBV and hence HBsAg positive.^[5] They are a potential source of HBV infection for other patients as well as for medical personnel. Based on observations across major medical college hospitals in Bangladesh, liver diseases account for 8–12% of total admissions in medicine wards and remain the third leading cause of death in tertiary care hospitals in the country.^[6] Patients admitted to hospital wards are often in advanced stages with overt clinical manifestations or complications. Some patients may present with vague digestive complaints with minimal physical signs. Differences in clinical presentation of jaundice have been observed in Bangladesh compared to

Western countries.^[7] This is consistent with findings that the majority of cases in this country are non-alcoholic and usually follow post-viral infection, whereas alcoholic cirrhosis is more common in Western populations. Among hepatotropic viruses, HBV is reported to be the most important, and the persistent presence of hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) is strongly associated with chronic parenchymal liver disease.^[8] Only a few studies have been conducted to detect the clinical presentation of jaundiced patients, but due to lack of adequate technical and laboratory support at that time, all etiologies could not be properly identified.^[9] The purpose of this dissertation is to review recent advances in this field and to study and analyze a series of one hundred cases of jaundiced patients admitted into the medicine unit of Chittagong Medical College Hospital with regard to their etiology and patterns of

clinical presentation. A provisional diagnosis will be made by routine investigations and the etiology will be established by special investigations. All necessary information will be recorded in a pre-designed structured case record form and the data will be processed and presented in tabular form. These findings may help in formulating appropriate management strategies and policy recommendations for handling such high-risk patients.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This was a cross-sectional observational hospital-based study conducted in the medicine wards of Chittagong Medical College Hospital (CMCH), Chittagong, Bangladesh, over a period of 12 months in the previous year. A total of 100 patients admitted with jaundice were enrolled consecutively. Data were collected using a pre-designed structured case record form including demographic variables, socioeconomic status, clinical presentation, laboratory investigations, and imaging findings. Jaundice was classified into

hepatocellular, obstructive, and haemolytic types based on clinical evaluation, biochemical parameters (serum bilirubin, liver enzymes, prothrombin time), and ultrasonographic findings. All patients underwent routine hematological and biochemical investigations, and ultrasonography where indicated. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and presented in tables and percentages.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged >12 years admitted with jaundice as a primary or significant presentation
- Patients or guardians providing informed consent
- Patients admitted to the medicine wards of CMCH during the study period

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients aged ≤12 years
- Patients managed entirely on an outpatient basis

- Patients unwilling to participate or undergo investigations

RESULTS

Out of 100 patients, hepatocellular jaundice accounted for 80 cases (80%), obstructive jaundice for 16 cases (16%), and haemolytic jaundice for 4 cases (4%). Among hepatocellular causes, viral hepatitis was the most common (43 cases), with hepatitis B virus (HBV) in 24 cases (30% of the group) and hepatitis E virus (HEV) in 18 cases (22.5%). Hepatocellular carcinoma was diagnosed in 15 cases (18.75%), chronic liver disease in 8 cases (10%), and autoimmune hepatitis in 4 cases (5%). In the obstructive group, carcinoma of the common bile duct was the leading cause (4 cases, 25% of the group), followed by cholelithiasis (3 cases), biliary ascariasis (3 cases), primary sclerosing cholangitis (2 cases), and choledocholithiasis (2 cases). All four haemolytic cases were due to beta-thalassaemia major (*Table I*).

Table I

Etiological diagnosis of 100 jaundice cases.

Diagnosis	n	% of group	% of total
I. Hepatocellular jaundice (N = 80, 80%)			
Viral hepatitis	43	53.75%	43.0%
Hepatitis B virus (HBV)	24	30.00%	24.0%
Hepatitis E virus (HEV)	18	22.50%	18.0%
Hepatitis C virus (HCV)	1	1.25%	1.0%
Hepatitis A virus (HAV)	0	0%	0%
Hepatocellular carcinoma	15	18.75%	15.0%
Chronic liver disease	8	10.00%	10.0%
Hepatitis — other causes (malaria, enteric fever)	6	7.50%	6.0%
Autoimmune hepatitis	4	5.00%	4.0%
Liver abscess	3	3.75%	3.0%
Drug-induced hepatitis (anti-tubercular)	1	1.25%	1.0%
II. Obstructive jaundice (N = 16, 16%)			
Carcinoma of common bile duct	4	25.00%	4.0%
Cholelithiasis	3	18.75%	3.0%
Biliary ascariasis	3	18.75%	3.0%
Primary sclerosing cholangitis	2	12.50%	2.0%
Choledocholithiasis	2	12.50%	2.0%
Carcinoma of head of pancreas	1	6.25%	1.0%
Carcinoma of gallbladder	1	6.25%	1.0%
III. Haemolytic jaundice (N = 4, 4%)			
Beta-thalassaemia major	4	100%	4.0%

The highest incidence of jaundice overall occurred in the 31–40 years age group (28% of total), followed by 21–30 years (21%) and 41–50 years (20%). Males outnumbered females overall (63 vs. 37, ratio 1.7:1). In the hepatocellular group,

67.5% were male; in the obstructive group, 62.5% were female; and the haemolytic group had equal sex distribution (50% each). The most common occupation was housewife (34%), followed by serviceman (16%) and farmer (15%).

Socioeconomically, 59% belonged to the middle class (5,000–15,000 BDT/month), 36% to the poor class (<5,000 BDT/month), and only 5% to the upper class (>15,000 BDT/month) *Table II*.

Table IIDemographic profile by jaundice type (*n* = 100).

Variable	Total (n=100)	Hepatocellular (n=80)	Obstructive (n=16)	Haemolytic (n=4)
Age group (years)				
11–20	14 (14%)	13 (16.3%)	1 (6.3%)	2 (50%)
21–30	21 (21%)	19 (23.8%)	1 (6.3%)	1 (25%)
31–40 (peak incidence)	28 (28%)	23 (28.8%)	3 (18.8%)	1 (25%)
41–50	20 (20%)	15 (18.8%)	5 (31.3%)	0
51–60	12 (12%)	9 (11.3%)	3 (18.8%)	0
61–70	5 (5%)	2 (2.5%)	3 (18.8%)	0
Sex distribution				
Male	63 (63%)	54 (67.5%)	6 (37.5%)	2 (50%)
Female	37 (37%)	26 (32.5%)	10 (62.5%)	2 (50%)

The most frequent symptoms overall were anorexia (87%), nausea and vomiting (80%), abdominal pain (79%), and weakness/fatigue/weight loss (74%). Fever was reported in 61% of cases. Pruritus was

observed in 87.5% of obstructive jaundice cases but only 27.5% of hepatocellular and none in haemolytic cases. Pale stools occurred in 50% of obstructive cases compared to 8.8% in hepatocellular cases.

Haemolytic jaundice typically presented with gradual onset (75%) and milder symptoms, whereas acute onset was more common in hepatocellular (72.5%) and obstructive (68.8%) groups (*Table III*).

Table III

Symptoms - overall frequency and comparison by jaundice type.

Symptom	Overall n (%)	Hepatocellular (n=80) n (%)	Obstructive (n=16) n (%)	Haemolytic (n=4) n (%)
Mode of onset				
Acute	70 (70%)	58 (72.5%)	11 (68.8%)	1 (25%)
Gradual	30 (30%)	22 (27.5%)	5 (31.3%)	3 (75%)
Symptoms				
Anorexia	87 (87%)	70 (87.5%)	16 (100%)	1 (25%)
Nausea & vomiting	80 (80%)	64 (80.0%)	15 (93.8%)	1 (25%)
Abdominal pain	79 (79%)	63 (78.8%)	13 (81.3%)	3 (75%)
Weakness / fatigue / weight loss	74 (74%)	58 (72.5%)	13 (81.3%)	3 (75%)
Fever	61 (61%)	49 (61.3%)	9 (56.3%)	3 (75%)
Pruritus (itching)	36 (36%)	22 (27.5%)	14 (87.5%)	0 (0%)
Abdominal swelling	26 (26%)	22 (27.5%)	4 (25.0%)	0 (0%)
Leg swelling	19 (19%)	18 (22.5%)	1 (6.3%)	0 (0%)
Bleeding (any site)	8 (8%)	3 (3.8%)	2 (12.5%)	1 (25%)
Facial swelling	2 (2%)	2 (2.5%)	0	0
Urine and stool colour				
High-coloured urine	87 (87%)	72 (90.0%)	14 (87.5%)	1 (25%)
Yellow stool	72 (72%)	64 (80.0%)	7 (43.8%)	1 (25%)
Pale stool	15 (15%)	7 (8.8%)	8 (50.0%)	0
Normal stool / urine	13 (13%)	8 (10.0%)	2 (12.5%)	1 (25%)

Below-average nutritional status was noted in 53% of all patients. Severe jaundice (clinical assessment) was seen in 36.3% of hepatocellular and 43.8% of obstructive cases, but absent in haemolytic cases. Hepatomegaly was common across all

groups, highest in obstructive jaundice (81.3%). Ascites was found exclusively in the hepatocellular group (35% of that group). Splenomegaly was most frequent in haemolytic jaundice (75%). Anaemia was universal (100%) in haemolytic cases.

Signs of hepatic encephalopathy (stupor/coma, fetor hepaticus), as well as gynaecomastia, testicular atrophy, and clubbing, were confined to the hepatocellular group (*Table IV*).

Table IV
Clinical signs - overall frequency and comparison by jaundice type.

Sign	Overall n (%)	Hepatocellular (n=80) n (%)	Obstructive (n=16) n (%)	Haemolytic (n=4) n (%)
Nutritional status				
Average	47 (47%)	39 (48.8%)	7 (43.8%)	1 (25%)
Below average	53 (53%)	41 (51.3%)	9 (56.3%)	3 (75%)
Severity of jaundice				
Mild	13 (13%)	10 (12.5%)	0 (0%)	3 (75%)
Moderate	51 (51%)	41 (51.3%)	9 (56.3%)	1 (25%)
Severe	36 (36%)	29 (36.3%)	7 (43.8%)	0 (0%)
Abdominal findings				
Hepatomegaly	67 (67%)	52 (65.0%)	13 (81.3%)	2 (50%)
Ascites	28 (28%)	28 (35.0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Splenomegaly	21 (21%)	15 (18.8%)	3 (18.8%)	3 (75%)
Enlarged gallbladder	3 (3%)	1 (1.3%)	2 (12.5%)	0 (0%)
Other signs				
Anaemia	25 (25%)	14 (17.5%)	7 (43.8%)	4 (100%)
Oedema	24 (24%)	22 (27.5%)	1 (6.3%)	1 (25%)
Clubbing	10 (10%)	10 (12.5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Engorged veins	9 (9%)	8 (10.0%)	1 (6.3%)	0 (0%)
Stupor / coma	13 (13%)	13 (16.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Tremor / convulsion	7 (7%)	6 (7.5%)	1 (6.3%)	0 (0%)
Fetor hepaticus	3 (3%)	3 (3.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Gynaecomastia	4 (4%)	4 (5.0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Testicular atrophy	5 (5%)	5 (6.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Leuconychia	6 (6%)	5 (6.3%)	1 (6.3%)	0 (0%)

Mean haemoglobin was markedly lower in haemolytic jaundice (5.7 ± 1.2 g/dl) compared to hepatocellular (11.6 ± 2.2 g/dl) and obstructive (10.6 ± 1.84 g/dl) groups. ESR was highest in obstructive (81.5 ± 46.2 mm/hr) and haemolytic (85 ± 36.9 mm/hr) groups, and lower in

hepatocellular cases (46.2 ± 38.3 mm/hr). Total WBC count was elevated in hepatocellular ($11,000 \pm 3,740$ /cmm) and obstructive ($10,020 \pm 3,000$ /cmm) groups but relatively normal in haemolytic cases ($7,150 \pm 2,300$ /cmm). All haemolytic cases had serum bilirubin ≤ 6 mg/dl. In

contrast, hepatocellular and obstructive cases showed a wide bilirubin range, including levels >30 mg/dl in a few patients (3.8% and 12.5%, respectively) *Table V*.

Table V
Haematological parameters and serum bilirubin distribution by jaundice type.

Parameter	Hepatocellular (n=80) Mean \pm SD (range)	Obstructive (n=16) Mean \pm SD (range)	Haemolytic (n=4) Mean \pm SD (range)
Haematological parameters			
Haemoglobin (g/dl)	11.6 ± 2.2 (7.5–16.2)	10.6 ± 1.84 (7.5–13.9)	5.7 ± 1.2 (4.1–6.9)
ESR (mm in 1st hour)	46.2 ± 38.3 (3–140)	81.5 ± 46.2 (18–140)	85 ± 36.9 (50–130)
Total WBC count (/cmm)	$11,000 \pm 3,740$ (6,200–19,000)	$10,020 \pm 3,000$ (6,800–15,000)	$7,150 \pm 2,300$ (4,800–9,000)
Serum bilirubin distribution (mg/dl)			
2.0–6.0	33 (41.3%)	3 (18.8%)	4 (100%)
6.1–10.0	9 (11.3%)	2 (12.5%)	0
10.1–14.0	14 (17.5%)	6 (37.5%)	0
14.1–18.0	7 (8.8%)	0	0
18.1–22.0	4 (5.0%)	2 (12.5%)	0
22.1–26.0	5 (6.3%)	0	0
26.1–30.0	5 (6.3%)	1 (6.3%)	0
>30.0	3 (3.8%)	2 (12.5%)	0

Mean haemoglobin was markedly lower in haemolytic jaundice (5.7 ± 1.2 g/dl) compared to hepatocellular (11.6 ± 2.2 g/dl) and obstructive (10.6 ± 1.84 g/dl) groups. ESR was highest in obstructive (81.5 ± 46.2 mm/hr) and haemolytic (85 ± 36.9 mm/hr) groups, and lower in

hepatocellular cases (46.2 ± 38.3 mm/hr). Total WBC count was elevated in hepatocellular ($11,000 \pm 3,740$ /cmm) and obstructive ($10,020 \pm 3,000$ /cmm) groups but relatively normal in haemolytic cases ($7,150 \pm 2,300$ /cmm). All haemolytic cases had serum bilirubin ≤ 6 mg/dl. In

contrast, hepatocellular and obstructive cases showed a wide bilirubin range, including levels >30 mg/dl in a few patients (3.8% and 12.5%, respectively) *Table VI*.

Table VI
Liver function tests by jaundice type.

Parameter / Range	Hepatocellular (n=80) n (%)	Obstructive (n=16) n (%)	Haemolytic (n=4) n (%)
Serum ALT/SGPT (IU/L)			
<40 (normal)	15 (18.8%)	3 (18.8%)	4 (100%)
41–300	41 (51.3%)	2 (12.5%)	0
301–1000	14 (17.5%)	6 (37.5%)	0
>1000	10 (12.5%)	0	0
Serum AST/SGOT (IU/L)			
<40 (normal)	15 (18.8%)	4 (25.0%)	2 (50%)
41–300	40 (50.0%)	12 (75.0%)	2 (50%)
301–1000	17 (21.3%)	0	0
>1000	7 (8.8%)	0	0
Serum alkaline phosphatase (IU/L)			
40–300 (normal/mildly raised)	20 (25.0%)	1 (6.3%)	4 (100%)
301–1000	38 (47.5%)	7 (43.8%)	0
>1000	5 (6.3%)	3 (18.8%)	0
Prothrombin time			
Within 4 sec of control (12–15 sec)	20 (25.0%)	6 (37.5%)	2 (50%)
Moderately prolonged (16–18 sec)	19 (23.8%)	7 (43.8%)	0
Markedly prolonged (>19 sec)	33 (41.3%)	3 (18.8%)	0

Ultrasonography was performed in 87 of 100 patients (67 hepatocellular, all 16 obstructive, and all 4 haemolytic). In the hepatocellular group, isolated hepatomegaly was the most common finding (50.8%), followed by space-occupying lesions suggestive of

hepatocellular carcinoma or liver abscess (26.9%). Hepatosplenomegaly was seen in 10.5% of hepatocellular cases. All biliary pathologies including mass in common bile duct (4 cases, 25% of obstructive group), biliary ascariasis (3 cases, 18.8%), cholelithiasis (3 cases, 18.8%),

choledocholithiasis (2 cases, 12.5%), mass in head of pancreas (1 case), and mass in gallbladder (1 case) were confined to the obstructive jaundice group. Haemolytic cases showed either hepatosplenomegaly (50%) or isolated splenomegaly (50%) *Table VII.*

Table VII
Ultrasonography findings by jaundice type.

Ultrasonographic finding	Hepatocellular (n=67*) n (%)	Obstructive (n=16) n (%)	Haemolytic (n=4) n (%)
Isolated hepatomegaly	34 (50.8%)	0	0
SOL suggestive of HCC / liver abscess	18 (26.9%)	0	0
Hepatosplenomegaly	7 (10.5%)	2 (12.5%)	2 (50%)
Isolated splenomegaly	4 (6.0%)	0	2 (50%)
Coarse hepatic parenchyma	4 (6.0%)	0	0
Mass in common bile duct	0	4 (25.0%)	0
Biliary ascariasis	0	3 (18.8%)	0
Cholelithiasis	0	3 (18.8%)	0
Choledocholithiasis	0	2 (12.5%)	0
Mass in head of pancreas	0	1 (6.3%)	0
Mass in gallbladder	0	1 (6.3%)	0

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated 100 consecutive jaundiced patients admitted to the medicine unit of Chittagong Medical College Hospital, classifying them into hepatocellular (80%), obstructive (16%), and haemolytic (4%) categories. The findings provide a comprehensive picture of the etiological spectrum, clinical features, and investigative profile of jaundiced patients in a tertiary care setting in Bangladesh. In this study, hepatocellular jaundice was the dominant category, accounting for 80% of all cases. Among hepatocellular causes, viral hepatitis was the single largest subgroup (43 cases, 53.75%), with HBV being the most common individual agent (24 cases, 30% of hepatocellular group) followed closely by HEV (18 cases, 22.5%). This pattern is similar to the findings of a landmark multi-centre surveillance study by Paul et al.^[10]

published in PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases (2020), which enrolled 1,925 acute jaundice patients from six tertiary hospitals across Bangladesh and found that HEV accounted for 34% of acute jaundice hospitalisations and HBV for 15%. The relatively higher HBV proportion in the present study may reflect case-mix differences, as this study included both acute and chronic hepatitis B presentations. A 2025 cross-sectional study from a tertiary hospital in Chattogram (July 2022–June 2023)^[11] similarly found HBV and HEV to be the two most prevalent hepatotropic viruses in the region, underscoring the sustained burden of these agents over time. The continued dominance of HBV is contextualised by national epidemiological data. Banik et al.^[4] in a systematic review and meta-analysis published in *Epidemiology & Infection* (2022), estimated the pooled prevalence of

HBV infection in Bangladesh at 4.0% (95% CI: 3.0–5.1%), confirming a low-intermediate but clinically significant level of endemicity. Hassan uz-Zaman et al.^[5] further documented sharp sociodemographic stratification of HBV prevalence, with awareness and risk exposure being key determinants. HEV is mainly waterborne, with a national serosurvey showing common infections across Bangladesh, especially in urban areas.^[12] The high representation of HEV in this hospital-based urban tertiary centre is therefore consistent with this epidemiological background. A notable observation was the complete absence of HAV among the 100 study cases. Historically, HAV was a significant cause of jaundice in Bangladesh; however, a 2022 overview of acute viral hepatitis in Bangladesh^[13] noted that childhood exposure to HAV has become near-

universal, with seroprevalence approaching 100% in children under six years of age, rendering clinical HAV hepatitis in hospitalised adults increasingly rare. This epidemiological shift parallels observations in other developing countries undergoing sanitary transition, where improved childhood exposure results in widespread natural immunity before adulthood.^[3] Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) was found in 15 cases (18.75% of the hepatocellular group), a strikingly high proportion reflecting the underlying chronic HBV burden.^[3] Regional data from India reinforce this finding; a three-year institutional study^[14] reported that cirrhosis was present in 73.2% of HCC patients and that over 60% presented at advanced BCLC stages C or D, highlighting the impact of limited screening access in resource-constrained environments. Autoimmune hepatitis accounted for 4 cases (5%), consistent with its expected contribution to hepatocellular disease within hospital-admitted jaundice populations.^[11] Obstructive jaundice constituted 16% of cases. The leading cause was carcinoma of the common bile duct (25%), followed equally by cholelithiasis and biliary ascariasis (18.75% each). The notable presence of biliary ascariasis an infection-related biliary obstruction reflects the poor sanitation conditions prevalent among the study population, 95% of whom belonged to the middle or poor socioeconomic class. A study on obstructive jaundice similarly identified biliary calculi and malignancy as the dominant causes of obstruction in a tertiary South Asian setting, though biliary parasitic infection was less prominent there due to regional differences.^[15] Female predominance in obstructive jaundice (62.5% female) in this series aligns with the well-established epidemiological predilection of cholelithiasis for females,^[1] a finding mirrored by a Brazilian cross-sectional obstructive jaundice cohort (2019)^[16] that also reported female predominance (58%). The demographic profile reveals peak jaundice incidence in the 31–40 year age group (28%), followed by 21–30 and 41–50 years consistent with the working-age burden of HBV and HEV infections in South Asia. The Paul et al.^[10] Bangladesh surveillance study confirmed that acute HEV predominantly affects young adult males aged 15–44 years, and the present study found an overall M:F ratio of 1.7:1, with male predominance strongest in the hepatocellular group (67.5% male). A 2023–2024 paediatric hepatitis study at Bangladesh Shishu Hospital^[17] similarly found 62% male predominance, suggesting a consistent sex-based pattern across age groups. Occupation and socioeconomic data with housewives (34%), service personnel

(16%), and farmers (15%) being the most common occupational groups further underscore that jaundice in this population predominantly affects economically active and domestically engaged individuals of lower-middle income. The symptom profile was dominated by anorexia (87%), nausea and vomiting (80%), abdominal pain (79%), and weakness or fatigue (74%), consistent with the classical presentation of viral hepatitis and biliary disease as described by Fargo et al.^[2] The stark differential in pruritus prevalence 87.5% in obstructive vs. 27.5% in hepatocellular cases reflects the pathophysiological accumulation of bile salts in skin that hallmarks extrahepatic obstruction.^[1] Pale stools (50% obstructive vs. 8.8% hepatocellular) and high-coloured urine (90% hepatocellular vs. 87.5% obstructive) further confirm the value of clinical symptom patterns in differentiating jaundice subtypes. Haemolytic jaundice characteristically presented with gradual onset (75%), milder general symptoms, and more prominent anaemia and splenomegaly. Laboratory investigations confirmed expected biochemical patterns. Hepatocellular jaundice showed marked transaminase elevation, with ALT exceeding 1,000 IU/L in 12.5% of hepatocellular cases, indicating severe parenchymal injury.^[18] Prothrombin time was markedly prolonged (>19 seconds) in 41.3% of the hepatocellular group, consistent with advanced coagulopathy. Obstructive cases were characterised by disproportionate alkaline phosphatase elevation (>300 IU/L in over 62.5%) and higher peak bilirubin levels, with 12.5% exceeding 30 mg/dl. The haemolytic group showed the classic triad of severe anaemia (mean Hb 5.7 ± 1.2 g/dl), elevated ESR (mean 85 ± 36.9 mm/hr) and mild bilirubin elevation (all ≤ 6 mg/dl), consistent with beta-thalassaemia major. Ultrasonography was diagnostically decisive for the obstructive group, correctly identifying biliary pathology in all 16 cases, consistent with evidence from a prospective Indian study confirming USG as a reliable first-line modality for biliary obstruction evaluation.^[19]

LIMITATION

This was a single-center hospital-based study with a relatively small sample size, limiting the generalizability of findings to the broader population.

CONCLUSION

Jaundice is a prevalent condition among hospital patients in Bangladesh, affecting individuals of all ages due to various causes. While timely diagnosis can lead to cures for some cases, the high cost of laboratory investigations hinders quick detection. This dissertation reviews recent

advancements in the field and evaluates the clinical patterns of jaundice, focusing on its etiology and presentation. A study of 100 adult jaundice patients from Chittagong Medical College Hospital over 12 months was conducted. The analysis showed that viral hepatitis is the leading cause of hepatocellular jaundice, while β -thalassaemia major is common in hemolytic cases. Key clinical features included anorexia, nausea, weight loss, and jaundice, with most patients coming from middle or lower economic backgrounds, especially in the younger age group (<40 years). Biochemical markers such as hyperbilirubinemia and elevated liver enzymes were common across all jaundice types. This preliminary study, limited to inpatients, highlights the need for larger, multicenter research for more comprehensive insights into jaundice in Bangladesh.

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